

Prosumers optimally adapted to local load. Rationale and benefits for the grid

Mihai Sanduleac
Faculty of Power Engineering
University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest
Bucharest, Romania
mihai.sanduleac@upb.ro

Dorel Stanescu
Department of Metering
Electrica Transilvania Sud
Brasov, Romania
dorel.stanescu@electrica-distributie.ro

Mihaela Albu
Faculty of El. Engineering
University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest
Bucharest, Romania
mihaela.albu@upb.ro

Carmen Stanescu
Metering Branch OMEPA
TSO 'Transelectrica'
Sibiu, Romania
carmen.stanescu@transelectrica.ro

Abstract—Prosumers are entities with an essential role in the new smart grid paradigm, having enabled two ways active power exchange. The usual approach is to send prosumer's excess energy to the main grid, with a cost of unpredictability of the reverse power flow. In order to achieve a high penetration of renewables in the distribution grid, with added contribution from prosumers, traditional grids need to be operated in states corresponding to active grids, for which they have not been originally designed. Recently deployed solutions allow advanced prosumers to benefit from advancements in both storage and renewables technologies, changing the behavior of prosumers into controlled unidirectional power exchange (no-back generation to the grid), which translates into consumer-only behavior from the grid side. With this no-back generation paradigm, in this paper a number of comprehensive scenarios have been simulated and analyzed on a daily basis, based on real local production and consumption profiles and using key performance indexes. The paper shows the benefits of operating and customers with prosumers potential, which can bring substantial openings for a high renewables penetration agenda to address climate change related issues.

Keywords— *prosumer; active distribution grid; RES; storage; Key Performance Indicator; energy meter; PCC*

I. INTRODUCTION

Prosumers are entities with an essential role in the new smart grid paradigm. In a so-called passive approach, they are connected to the distribution grid and potentially correlate the local production of electricity, usually from photovoltaic (PV) systems, with the local load (self-consumption) when that production and consumption are simultaneous (power curves matching); the “active” approach corresponds to the case when electricity in excess (positive difference of generated power and local loading) is injected into the main (distribution) grid [1]. This “active” operation of prosumers (equivalent to a negative load in the PCC) has mainly three drawbacks: (i) the

energy injected in the grid is sold using a non attractive feed-in tariff, usually lower than the price of purchased energy; (ii) the grid operation is not optimal, due to the fact that it has been designed for one direction transfer of the electricity (from grid towards the loads, positive power flow) only; and (iii) the changing regulatory environment which adds uncertainty to the prosumer economic scenario [2]. To cope with those issues and following the advancement of electricity storage like affordable battery systems as a direct result of the development of (electrical) mobility, a solution is proposed in [3]; it makes possible to improve the self-consumption capacity, up to achieving no-back generation towards the grid. This solution is analyzed in the paper considering the present (2019) Romanian regulatory environment.

Starting with 2018, in Romania, prosumers having power generation modules using renewable resources (RES) and with a nominal power of no more than 27 kW are allowed to sell to the electricity suppliers (with whom contracts for the supply of electricity have been agreed) the electricity produced on the spot and delivered to the electricity grid, according to ANRE regulations [4].

However, specific regulations to the generation units apply: in normal grid operation the active power generation unit must not produce quick voltage variations greater than $\pm 5\%$ from the nominal grid voltage in the Point of Common Coupling (PCC). In addition, it must prove that the power quality in the PCC is in line with current standards [5] and Electricity Distribution Grid Standard of Performance [6]. The connection solution of the active power injector with nominal power of less than 1 MW shall not allow islanded operation. The integration of the electrical energy storage system into the active power plant (the prosumer installations) should be designed in such a way that the electrical diagram allows the direct measurement of the electricity produced from renewable

sources, when entirely or part of it is delivered to the electricity grid [7, 8].

In Romania, state financing is provided for prosumers, using the 'Program for the installation of photovoltaic panels systems for the production of electricity in order to cover the consumption needs and surplus delivery in the national network' [9]. Its purpose is to fund the acquisition and installation of RES-based energy systems, and to increase energy efficiency, improve air quality and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The objective of the program is to increase the capacities to produce electricity from renewable sources, and the performance indicator is the total amount of greenhouse gases (kg CO₂) reduced by the installation of photovoltaic panels systems calculated throughout the project monitoring period [9, 10].

II. STORAGE CONTROL ALGORITHMS AND KPIS

In order to optimally match the local electricity production with the load, an electricity storage unit has to be locally connected and its operation controlled as to achieve in the prosumer' PCC a positive (or zero) active power exchange with the grid. The storage control algorithm is implementing the UniRCon approach [2], meaning controlling and planning the prosumer's internal resources such that there is no injection of electricity towards the main grid, enabling a positive power flow from grid perspective.

The no-back generation algorithm comprises of the following steps: a) it measures (in the numerical simulation it estimates) the electrical energy exchanged with the DSO in PCC and considers a variable ΔP_{DSO} (back generation) to be set to zero by using local prosumer's resources; b) it calculates the share of the ΔP_{DSO} which can be solved by changing the battery inverter setpoint, to use locally as much as possible from the electricity generated; c) if there is unsolved ΔP due to, for example, high level of battery state of charge (SoC) or limitations in the power level of the battery inverter, a local curtailment of the PV generation is applied; to be noted that a local demand response or request to share electricity with neighbors may be also possible, however this possibility is not addressed in this paper; d) when battery SoC is over a predefined limit and the PV production is not available (evening, clouds etc.), the required power to be taken from the distribution grid is minimized by using the battery in discharging mode. Some other control variables are also considered in order to make the daily schedule more robust.

To assess the performance of a daily cycle, the following several Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are introduced. The main KPIs used for assessing the prosumer's behavior for an assessment horizon $T_{W_KPI} = 1$ day are:

$$KPI_1 = K_{USER_E_BACK} = E_{PCC-} / E_{CONS} \quad (1)$$

$$KPI_2 = K_{PV_CURT} = E_{PV_CURT} / E_{PV_METEO} \quad (2)$$

$$KPI_3 = K_{USER_E_DSO} = E_{PCC+} / E_{CONS} \quad (3)$$

$$KPI_4 = K_{AUTO_CONS} = E_{PV} / E_{CONS} \quad (4)$$

where:

E_{PCC-} is the energy injected back into the grid in the PCC, for the observation window T_{W_KPI} ;

E_{CONS} is the electricity locally consumed in the prosumer's installations (loads different than storage in charging mode);

E_{PV_CURT} is the daily curtailed energy from PV

E_{PV_METEO} is the daily PV energy without curtailment

E_{PCC+} is the electricity exchanged (consumed from the grid, having the consumer convention of power, which is plus) in the PCC, for the observation window T_{W_KPI} ;

E_{PV} is the electricity generated locally (by the PV panels on the prosumer' premises) for the observation window T_{W_KPI} ;

The KPIs have the following meaning:

$KPI_1 = K_{USER_E_BACK}$ is quantifying how much excess of electricity has been produced in comparison with the prosumer loading for the observation window T_{W_KPI} ; this indicator shall be, ideally, as low as possible; it quantifies the level α of an acceptable back-generation, e.g. of up to 5% of the daily load of the prosumer or of the approved "connection power in load mode": for $\alpha=5\%$ KPI_1 is in the range [0, 0.05].

$KPI_2 = K_{PV_LIM}$ is quantifying the level of PV potential curtailment is needed for the observation window T_{W_KPI} ;

$KPI_3 = K_{USER_E_DSO}$ is quantifying the percentage of consumed energy which is coming from the DSO grid; the lower is KPI_3 , the better is the resilience against outages;

$KPI_4 = K_{AUTO_CONS} = E_{PV} / E_{CONS}$ is quantifying the ratio of PV local generation which is self-consumed. It is advisable in the design phase to be as high as possible, however an average value less than 1 is a signal of a good planning and selection of storage and PV investment for a given local consumption.

KPI_1 is computed in two ways: the first one is based on an ideal automation scheme, which brings always a zero back-generation due to instantaneous reaction ($KPI_{1,1}$); the second one is obtained by simulating a real automation scheme, which is supposed to react to the PCC back generation during each observation time interval, but with a limited reaction speed. As the observation period T_{w_obs} is one minute, it is considered that the automation is able to completely react to the unbalance in half of this time, meaning in 30 seconds. In reality, the time of reaction can be in the limits of one to 10 seconds, but for covering more demanding situations, it has been considered an unbalanced operation with duration T_{w_react} of 30 seconds.

III. SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

In order to have a comprehensive view of the prosumer's no-back generation (UniRCon) algorithm, a number of 12 different consumption profiles and 10 different production profiles have been considered. The profiles are obtained from real-data profiles recorded each 1 minute and (uniformly) scaled such that they fit with the designed UniRCon approach. It means that the PV production is dimensioned in such a way in most cases the daily energy PV production is not exceeding the daily energy consumption. Further, a procedure of pairing load and production profiles has been considered, in order to simulate a number of 17 different scenarios.

The Figure 1 shows that energy production is always less than energy consumption over a whole day, except one situation (scenario 12).

Fig. 1. Electricity local consumption and production scenarios

The figures below show the simulation panel and evolution of different values in two of the analyzed scenarios (Fig. 2, Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, Fig. 5 respectively) and the evolution of values in additional three scenarios (Fig. 6 to 8).

Fig. 2. Scenario 1 – Simulation panel

Fig. 3. Scenario 1 – Evolution in time of the active power information [W] retrieved from measurements

This scenario combines an evening peak consumption profile (P_{CONS} , blue line, on the part with positive/higher power on the graph) with a partially sunny PV evolution (P_{PV_METEO} and $P_{PV_after_curtail}$, red and green lines respectively, on the part with negative/lower power on the graph, with more cloudy periods at the end of the daylight period). The state of charge SoC (light green, in upper part of the graph) is nearly reaching

100% after charging during the daytime and going down under 20% at the end of the day. Fig. 2 shows values at the end of the day, useful for calculating the KPIs introduced in section II. Figure 4 uses the same PV production but with a different pattern of consumption.

Fig. 4. Scenario 5 – Evolution in time of the active power information [W] retrieved from measurements

In Figure 5, Scenario 6 uses another patterns for both consumption and production, having a low production characteristic, typically for a more cloudy day. It can be seen that the battery is not fully used, its SoC reaching only half of the total capacity (the 4 kW on vertical axis corresponds to the total capacity (the 4 kW on vertical axis corresponds to SoC = 100%). As opposite, Fig. 6, corresponding to Scenario 12, has a sunny full day (lower part of the graphs shows the PV evolution as having the classical “bel” shape), while consumption is low and only with some arbitrary peaks. For this pairing of consumption/production, the battery is fully used and only for a small period of time curtailment of the PV production is needed (red and green lower shapes do not match for more than one hour in the afternoon).

Fig. 5. Scenario 6 – Evolution in time of the active power information [W] retrieved from measurements

Fig. 6. Scenario 12 – Evolution in time of the active power information [W] retrieved from measurements

Scenario 15 from Fig. 7 presents irregular shapes for both production and consumption, with peaks during the daytime, making storage useful only for very short periods. It is a case when the storage is operated within a partial charge/discharge cycle, its lifetime being also preserved, as the maximal number of full cycles can be obtained with a higher number of partial cycles.

Fig. 7. Scenario 15 – Evolution in time of the active power information [W] retrieved from measurements

The reason for selecting a variety of production and consumption profiles (measurement data), was to allow a realistic analysis of the no-back generation algorithm, in various different situations, and the impact on the distribution grid.

IV. ASSESSMENT AND SYNTHESIS

For each scenario have been recorded evolutions of measurements and have been calculated the KPIs presented in previous section.

Figure 8 presents 12 consumption profiles which are used in the 17 scenarios, showing a large variety of shapes.

Fig. 8. Daily consumption profiles used to build scenarios (active power [W] retrieved from 1-minute reporting rate measurements)

Figure 9 presents the daily PV production in a selected set of 10 days, having various profiles of production, in order to catch the large spectrum of potential generation and consumption daily power curves during three seasons: spring, summer and autumn. Winter time has been not considered, as the production is usually very low and the consumption tends to be higher than in the considered study, thus giving too much optimistic situations for our study, with KPIs showing always a good situation. The winter period is therefore naturally fitting the UniRCon approach.

Fig. 9. Daily PV production profiles used to build scenarios (1-minute average powers)

The pairs of consumption versus production are presented in the Fig. 11. The 1-minute average power as seen on PCC without any local EMS algorithm, as seen by a “net metering” device, meaning the algebraical summation of the local PV production and of the consumption is depicted in figure below:

Fig. 10. EMS with “no-back generation” (UniRCon) – Power evolution at PCC for each scenario

The 1-minute based power obtained by aggregating the 17 scenarios (acting like a virtual community) show for the no-back generation algorithm a relatively low band of power evolution at the PCC of the virtual community – comparing with a non-controlled, “dummy” prosumer, as per Fig. 16.

Fig. 11. EMS with “no-back generation” (UniRCon) – Power evolution of aggregated scenarios (virtual community)

The power varies between nearly zero and 14 kW and shows net benefits for the distribution grid, comparing with the

variation from Fig. 13 and Fig. 14. Fig. 18 shows the difference between the two situations.

Fig. 12. Comparison of power exchange at PCC: classic and UniRCon

It can be seen that the total variation of power in PCC has an average of 7.63 kW in a classic, non-regulated prosumer environment; the no-back generation control not only that avoids the back generation, but also reduces the total variation of power in PCC at 4.57 kW, meaning around 40% lower variation. This lower variation of power over a day is expected to contribute also to lower voltage variations in the PCC, asking for less operational measures to keep within the required power quality levels (such as tap changing in the MV/LV transformer, control of reactive power and grid reconfiguration) [4].

The selected KPIs resulted for each scenario are presented in Table 1.

TABLE I. KEYS PERFORMANCE INDICATOR

Scenario	KPI ₁ [%]	KPI _{1,2} [%]	KPI ₂ [%]	KPI ₃ [%]	KPI ₄ [%]
Scen.1.1	0	1.47	0	37.25	66.30
Scen.1.2	0	1.47	3.98	35.43	66.30
Scen.1.3	0	1.47	14.44	41.19	66.30
Scen.1.4	0	2.15	0	33.52	75.98
Scen.1.5	0	1.13	0	29.73	78.36
Scen.1.6	0	1.24	0	61.91	35.19
Scen.1.7	0	0.79	34.61	35.16	96.01
Scen.1.8	0	0.79	27.26	29.25	96.01
Scen.1.9	0	0.79	19.41	29.35	96.01
Scen.1.10	0	1.02	0	45.70	3.59
Scen.1.11	0	1.4	0	36.69	82.04
Scen.1.12	0	1.06	1.38	32.70	110.63
Scen.1.13	0	0.88	0	41.16	63.81
Scen.1.14	0	1.04	0	54.15	74.47
Scen.1.15	0	1.72	0	45.70	53.51
Scen.1.16	0	0.87	0.12	52.34	86.53
Scen.1.17	0	1.01	2.47	44.54	86.87
Average	0	1.19	6.1	40.3	76.3

To be observed that the ideal KPI_{1,1} is zero in all the considered use-cases, as the automation to block back generation is considered able to work instantaneously. KPI_{1,2} shows real implementable automation which has a reaction time of half of the observed time (30 seconds for observability timeframes of 1 minute). Even in the simulation of longer time-reaction (50% of the observability time frame), KPI_{1,2} is always

below 2.5%, which suggests that a value of $\alpha=5\%$ energy sent back to the grid, due to the automation delays, is a feasible condition for a no-back generation prosumer.

KPI₂ gives the curtailment factor, which has an average of 6.1%. Scenarios 3, 4, 6, 7 and 10 have a limited storage of 8 kWh, Scenario 2 has 10 kWh of storage and the rest of scenarios have 12 kWh of available storage. One can see that the highest PV curtailment occurred in low storage availability conditions, and only one scenario (1.9) is higher even with the 12 kWh storage. A revisited 12 kWh storage value for all scenarios gives an average of curtailment with less than 3%, which is highly acceptable in the condition that no-back generation is attended and no-neighbor energy exchange is enabled. It is expected that an architecture based on a community energy exchange of excess energy may overpass even better the small curtailment occurred in some of the studied scenarios.

KPI₃ shows a low consumption from the grid, with an average of 40% from all considered scenarios, which shows the potential for a certain level of resilience.

KPI₄ validates the investment decision (i.e. storage dimensioning as related with the anticipated PV production to cope with the consumption in a no-back generation paradigm), and it is below 100% in almost all situations. Scenario 2 is the only one when it has been produced more energy than consumed, however a refined storage control algorithm and possible exchange of energy in a local energy community may avoid even more excess energy situations.

V. BENEFITS FOR THE GRID

Fig. 15 and Fig. 17 show in detail the difference of operation (and associated benefits) between classic (no controlled) prosumer and the proposed no-back generation prosumer (UnirCON). While Fig. 15 shows that during $T_{w_KPI}=1$ day there is electricity injection (active power) in the grid, thus contributing to the negative effects of active behavior of the distribution network, the no-back generation prosumer has a much friendlier interaction with the grid, keeping it in the “business-as-usual” consumption only profile. In the simulated scenarios, the total variation of power exchange with the grid is decreasing from 7.63 kW to 4.57 kW, which is a loading decrease of 40%. Keeping voltage level in the acceptable limits - as part of power quality portfolio, mitigating potential high voltage levels during the middle of the day and low voltage levels during the evening peak is not only a difficult task for the grid operator, but also a highly stressing challenge, while this situation repeats almost daily. Classic countermeasures, such as transformer plot change, reactive power control where possible or topology change are stressful and difficult measures to be used on a regular basis. The no-back generation behavior of advanced prosumers guarantees a return to the grid operation in the way how it has been initially designed. This “soft” plugging of the prosumer in the existing distribution grids gives also opening for high penetration of RES-based generation, without expecting DSO searching for solutions able to protect its business as usual. It is a technical win-win solution for the grid operator as well as for the prosumer.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents the benefits of prosumers acting as no-back generation entities, by using its local production, consumption and storage controlled by an EMS in such a way that the grid sees the prosumer as a consumption only entity, thus keeping the business as usual operation of the distribution grid.

It can be also seen that the level of variation of power exchange in the PCC is much smaller in case of the proposed no-back generation prosumer comparing with a classic prosumer, suggesting a lower stress on the distribution grid and the possibility to increase the capacity of the grid by avoiding reinforcement and to decrease the daily burden on the grid operation conditions; it also increase voltage level stability, as part of the power quality indicators.

The paper introduces several KPIs describing the proposed daily operation of the prosumer with no-back generation and suggests that a small value of no-back generation ratio α (of up to 5%) from the average consumption allows credible implementations of the automation to implement active power control in the PCC.

As a final observation, the proposed KPIs give expected results, on each scenario and also on average, suggesting that the no-back generation approach, with good dimensioning of resources versus consumption in the prosumer premises, has benefits for both prosumer and DSO.

As a final conclusion, the friendlier interaction of the no-back generation prosumer enables a higher penetration of RES in the grid, thus better addressing climate change concerns by bringing additional prosumer advantages, related to resilience, immunity, energy efficiency and clean energy solutions.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Albu, Mihaela; Sanduleac, Mihai.; Dorel, Stanescu; Carmen, Stanescu 'Meter Accuracy in Renewable Energy Sources-based Prosumer Nodes' Proc. of the IEEE 7th International Conference on Modern Power Systems (MPS 2017), Cluj Napoca, Romania, ID 34, June 2017.
- [2] Sanduleac, M.; Ciornei, Irina; Albu, Mihaela; Toma, L; Sturzeanu, Marta; Martins, JF, 'Resilient Prosumer Scenario in a Changing Regulatory Environment-The UniRCon Solution', *Energies* 2017, 10(7), 857.
- [3] Mihai Sanduleac, Mihaela Albu, Lucian Toma, João Martins, Anabela Gonçalves Pronto, Vasco Delgado-Gomes, 2017, Hybrid AC and DC Smart home resilient Architecture Transforming prosumers in UniRCons – Proc. of ICE 2017 IEEE TMC Europe Conference, July 2017
- [4] ANRE, Ordinul nr. 226/2018 'Regulile de comercializare a energiei electrice produse în centrale electrice din surse regenerabile cu putere electrică instalată de cel mult 27 kW aparținând prosumatorilor', in Romanian.
- [5] EN 50160, ed.2 "Voltage characteristics of electricity supplied by public distribution system";
- [6] ANRE, Romania, 2016, "The Electricity Distribution Grid – Standard of performance"
- [7] ANRE, Ordinul nr. 227/2018 'Contractul-cadru de vânzare-cumpărare a energiei electrice produse de prosumatorii care dețin centrale electrice de producere a energiei electrice din surse regenerabile cu puterea instalată de cel mult 27 kW pe loc de consum și pentru modificarea unor reglementări din sectorul energiei electrice', in Romanian.
- [8] ANRE, Ordinul nr. 228/2018 'Condiții tehnice de racordare la rețelele electrice de interes public pentru prosumatorii cu injecție de putere activă în rețea', Technical Norm, in Romanian.
- [9] Romanian Government Ministry of the Environment, 'Program for the installation of photovoltaic panels systems for the production of electricity in order to cover the consumption needs and surplus delivery in the national network', in Romanian.
- [10] Romanian National Energy Regulatory Authority, "The establishment for the promotion system of the production of energy from renewable sources of energy", Law No 220/2008.